

Assessing the Leadership Behaviors of Selected Academic Managers during the Pandemic: Implications for Enhancing Leadership Practices

¹Ma. Leah C. Tabile, ²Eduard M. Riparip, ³Alnee Joy A. Azul, ⁴Honey Liza C. Tamayo, ⁵Sonia Janice L. Pilao, ⁶Jean Marie I. Villanueva
Centro Escolar University, Makati City
¹mctabile@ceu.edu.ph, ²emriparip@ceu.edu.ph, ³ajaazul@ceu.edu.ph, ⁴hfconstantino@ceu.edu.ph,
⁵spilao@ceu.edu.ph, ⁶jvillanueva@ceu.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 4 April 2026
Revised: 10 April 2026
Accepted: 14 April 2026
Published: 26 April 2026
Corresponding Email:
emriparip@ceu.edu.ph

Recommended Citation:

Tabile, M. L. C., Riparip, E. M., Azul, A. J., Tamayo, H. L. C., Pilao, S.J., & Villanueva, J. M. I. (2026). Assessing the Leadership Behaviors of Selected Academic Managers during the Pandemic: Implications for Enhancing Leadership Practices. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*. 1 (4), 403-413.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19783246>

Index Terms:

crisis leadership, academic leaders, path-goal theory, leadership behaviors, COVID-19 pandemic

Abstract. The pandemic has forced educational institutions to transition to remote online learning, challenging academic leaders to face an unprecedented crisis while ensuring the continuity of quality education. This study explores the perceived leadership behaviors of academic managers at Centro Escolar University (CEU) during the COVID-19 pandemic and draws implications for enhancing leadership practices in times of crisis. Drawing on House's path-goal theory, this research examines how different leadership behaviors—directive, participative, supportive, and achievement-oriented—are exhibited by CEU academic managers in response to the health crisis' demands. The study's findings indicate that while all four leadership behaviors were evident among the leaders, participative leadership was the most commonly practiced. This style involves democratic leadership such as consulting with subordinates, encouraging their input in decision-making processes, and fostering a collaborative environment. The challenges faced by these academic leaders, including balancing compassion with performance expectations, maintaining visibility and communication with top management, and managing stress and work-life balance, are highlighted as critical factors impacting their effectiveness during the crisis. The results suggest that successful academic leadership in times of crisis requires adaptability and a keen understanding of the situational demands. Leaders should be flexible in their approach, shifting their leadership styles as needed to meet the evolving needs of their teams and institutions. The study concludes by recommending that educational leaders be trained to recognize and adjust their leadership behaviors according to the specific challenges and opportunities presented by crises, thereby enhancing their ability to lead effectively and maintain educational standards even in the most challenging circumstances.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought immense challenges in the education sector in the Philippines. One of these is the implementation of purely remote online learning, which is the optimal highlight of the educational experience of all the stakeholders, i.e. students and their parents, the teachers, and the academic leaders, amidst this health crisis.

In times of uncertainty, academic leadership plays a vital role toward the achievement of successful online learning. Academic leaders must rise to the educational leadership challenge, and "consider how to weave remote learning into the teaching and learning experiences of their schools" (Pont, 2020). This health emergency has become a valuable opportunity for school leaders to reimagine the delivery of education in ways that are suited to the 21st century.

As early as the end of the first quarter of 2020, education administrators and managers started customizing, redesigning, and recalibrating the pre-pandemic syllabi and curricula of their respective schools. The decisions to determine the most essential learning skills to be included in their instructional materials lie in the hands of the deans, department heads, program heads, principals, and academic coordinators.

Caught in the unique position of being the pinch point in the system, school leaders depend on COVID-19 responses, processes, procedures, and protocols from the government, which can change, almost overnight, depending on how the virus develops (Harris & Jones, 2020). These academic leaders, as well as the teachers, have done an immeasurable amount of hard work in the implementation of online learning despite the restrictions. Their leadership spells out the success of the execution of the online learning in the Philippines.

Tatlah and Iqbal (2012) explain that people commonly believe that leaders make a difference and want to understand why. This is true as students and teachers rely on the policies of school leaders during the pandemic. As Bass (1990) states, "leadership is often regarded as the single most important factor in the success or failure of institutions." To which Ogawa and Scribner (2002) agree, stating that "leaders are largely responsible for school performance." The success of the online learning and teaching process in schools are also indicative of school leadership's effectiveness.

The present study examines the different behaviors of educational leadership, a multidimensional area of research in behavioral and social sciences, that are employed by academic leaders during the pandemic. In particular, the program heads and academic department heads of Centro Escolar University were surveyed using House's path-goal theory questionnaire, which was modified by the researcher to suit the current situation.

The present research was conducted to determine the leadership behaviors employed by CEU academic managers such as department heads and program heads during the pandemic by using the Path-Goal Theory. It also analyzed the leadership experiences of the academic heads amidst a health crisis and how this affected their performance as leaders. The results of the study were used to draw implications for enhancing leadership practices, especially during a crisis.

Literature Review

Nature of school leadership

Day and Sammons (2014) examined the nature and purposes of school leadership and its relationships to school improvement. The study also focused on the link between school processes and leadership and how these can support better teaching and learning. Empirically, it found out that effective leadership is important but not a sufficient condition for successful schools.

In addition, the aforesaid study drew attention to two concepts of leadership: instructional/pedagogical and transformational. Evidence showed that pedagogical leadership is essential for promoting improved academic outcomes for learners, but it is concluded that the two forms of leadership are not mutually exclusive.

It added that there must be a synergy of strategies that warrant success and promote student outcomes by supporting and enhancing conditions for teaching and learning through direct impacts on teachers and their work. Moreover, school leaders play a vital role in setting the direction and developing a positive school culture. They can also help improve the morale of the school's staff and students by motivating and supporting them.

Pont, Nusche, and Moorman (2008), in an OECD report titled, *Improving School Leadership*, briefly reviewed the ever-changing landscape of school management over the last decades. They expounded on the role of school leadership, an integral part of education policy, in producing quality graduates and influencing school climate and environment. It influences the attitudes and beliefs of teachers, students, non-academic staff, as well as the environment in which they operate.

The report also states "in this new environment, schools and schooling are being given an ever bigger job to do. Greater decentralization in many countries is being coupled with more school autonomy, more accountability for school and student results, and a better use of the knowledge base of education and pedagogical processes. It is also being coupled with broader responsibility for contributing to and supporting the schools' local communities, other schools and other public services" (p.6).

Modern educational problems require modern solutions. Many states now have moved toward decentralization, making schools more autonomous in their decision-making and holding them more accountable for results (Pont, Nusche, & Moorman, 2008). This trend in leadership is demanded "by a demanding set of roles which include financial and human

resource management and leadership for learning.” Hence, the rise of educational leadership has become a priority for education policymakers. They need to create a sustainable framework that enhances the quality of school leadership.

Good curriculum, qualified teachers, state-of-the art facilities, student achievements, and sound policies are not the only indicators of successful schools. A report of Pont, Nusche and Moorman (2008) states that the educational needs of the 21st century also are dependent on the roles of school leadership, which have to be more dynamic and become far more than an administrator of top-down rules and regulations. In addition, school owners or the board must let the school leaders develop and implement strategies and procedures that help improve the learning and academic performance of their students. Hence, a manageable intervention is needed.

According to Hoy and Smith (2007), the principal is the single most important factor that influences the overall effectiveness of a school. This statement serves as a reminder for leaders to be aware of their leadership style and have a plan in place to improve their school. The leadership styles that are predominantly enacted by school administrators play an integral role in the functioning of all aspects of a school.

Leaders are key to the success of schools. They influence the attitudes and behaviors of their staff and students, and these influence the students’ learning and development and work performance of the staff. This emphasis has been placed on the contributions of school leaders in a successful school management. This is evidenced by the growing popularity of the instructional leadership (Day and Sammons, 2014).

Research Framework

The path-goal theory by House was used in the present study. Path-goal theory is about how leaders motivate followers to accomplish designated goals. It first appeared in the leadership literature in the early 1970s in the works of Evans (1970), House (1971), House and Dessler (1974), and House and Mitchell (1974). The stated goal of this leadership theory is to enhance follower performance and follower satisfaction by focusing on follower motivation.

It emphasizes the relationship between the leader's style and the characteristics of the followers and the organizational setting. For the leader, the imperative is to use a leadership style that best meets followers' motivational needs. This is done by choosing behaviors that complement or supplement what is missing in the work setting. Leaders' try to enhance followers' goal attainment by providing information or rewards in the work environment (Indvik, 1986).

According to House and Mitchell (1974), leadership generates motivation when it increases the number and kinds of payoffs that followers receive from their work. Leadership also motivates when it makes the path to the goal clear and easy to travel through coaching and direction, removing obstacles and roadblocks to attaining the goal, and making the work itself more personally satisfying.

House and Mitchell (1974) identified four categories of leadership behavior. Directive leader gives subordinates clear and specific instructions to perform their tasks, the timeline for task, and the standards of performance measurement. Supportive leader shows concern for the wellbeing and needs of the subordinates and treat them as equals. Participative leader involves subordinates in decision making by asking for ideas, opinions and takes their suggestions into account. The final leader behavior identified is Achievement-Oriented which involves creating challenging and high standard performance goals for subordinates and seeks for continuous improvement by showing great confidence in subordinates.

House (1996) says that Path-Goal theory was stimulated by Evan’s (1970) paper, “The effects of Supervisory Behavior on the Path-Goal Relationship” and expectancy theory of motivation. House and Mitchell (1974) define the strategic functions of a leader as (1) understanding and stimulating subordinates’ needs for outcomes, (2) enhancing followers’ incentives in order to motivate them for attainment of goals, (3) helping the followers to step forward in order to achieve those incentives, (4) making the followers understand what is expected of them, and (5) reducing those barriers which create frustrations and enhance chances that effective performance results in personal satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive survey research design. Descriptive research is used to systematically describe the characteristics, perceptions, or behaviors of a particular group or phenomenon without manipulating variables (Creswell, 2014). The design is appropriate for studies that aim to obtain information about existing conditions and to describe the current status of a population.

In this study, the descriptive survey design was utilized to determine the perceived leadership behaviors of academic managers during the pandemic based on the Path-Goal Theory of Leadership proposed by House (2008). Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation in order to summarize the responses of the participants.

Research Participants

The participants of the study were the academic department heads and program heads of Centro Escolar University across its three campuses: CEU Manila, CEU Makati, and CEU Malolos. A total of 25 academic managers participated in the survey. The participants were selected because of their direct involvement in academic leadership and administrative decision-making within the university during the pandemic period.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a validated questionnaire developed by House (2008), which is based on the Path-Goal Theory of Leadership. The instrument was used to determine the leadership behaviors of the respondents in terms of directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leadership styles.

The questionnaire was administered through an online survey form using Google Forms. Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, written informed consent was obtained from the participants to ensure voluntary participation and adherence to ethical research standards.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon the approval of the research proposal, the researchers sent an email letter to the Senior Vice President for Academic Affairs to conduct the study online. After the approval of the request, the online survey form was sent to the academic heads of CEU Manila, CEU Makati, and CEU Malolos. The participants were given more than a week to complete the survey. Following this, the answers from the Google Form were encoded for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the conduct of the study:

For the profile of the respondents, frequency and percentage formula were used. Mean and Standard Deviation were also used in treating the results of the survey.

Since questionnaire was on a Likert Scale, the following verbal interpretation was utilized:

5.17-6.00	Strongly Agree
4.33-5.16	Agree
3.50-4.32	Slightly Agree
2.67-3.49	Slightly Disagree
1.83-2.66	Disagree
1.00-1.82	Strongly Disagree

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical research standards to protect the rights and welfare of the participants. Ethical principles such as informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any time were strictly observed. Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was obtained from the university administrators of Centro Escolar University. All participants were provided with an informed consent form explaining the purpose of the study, their role in the research, and the voluntary nature of their participation. The collected data were treated with strict confidentiality and were used solely for research purposes. After the completion of the study and analysis, all data were securely deleted to prevent any misuse.

Results and Discussion

The following shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered from the academic managers, who are the subjects of the study.

Profile of the Participants

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
29-40 years old	4	16
41-50 years old	11	44
51-60 years old	7	28
60 years and above	3	12
Total	25	100

Table 1. Age of the Participants

Table 1 shows that 44 percent or 11 of the academic leader-respondents are aged between 41 to 50 years old. This is similar to England's median age for teachers, which is 48 years old (School leadership in England 2010 to 2016: characteristics and trends, 2018). However, in the Philippines, Guiab and Ganal (2014) found out that the average age of public school heads is between 51 to 55 years old. In the United States, the age bracket of a school leader or academic leader is 51.7 years (Hill, Ottem, & DeRoche, 2016).

On the other hand, Mandap (2023) stated that a millennial school head, aged between 26 and 41 years old, employs four significant themes: transformational leadership style, servant leadership style, instructional leadership style, and authoritative leadership style. The study added that millennial school leaders intentionally adopted these leadership styles to tackle the challenges they encounter in overseeing educational institutions.

The aforesaid studies have provided an opportunity for some teachers to advance to leadership positions sooner in their careers than their older peers, and has consequently resulted in an overall younger population of teachers in leadership roles. The data shows that the school leaders are becoming younger each year, veering away from seniority in an educational organization.

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	7	28
Female	18	72
Total	25	100

Table 2. Gender of the Participants

In Table 2, it shows that the female-academic leaders dominated the middle management, comprising 72 percent of the total number of department heads in CEU. This demonstrates the active role of women in leading organizations by crafting policies and guidelines.

Years of Service	Frequency	Percent (%)
0-5 years	7	28
6-10 years	6	24
11-20 years	10	40
21-30 years	1	4
31 years and above	1	4
Total	25	100

Table 3. Participants' Years of Service as a Head

The average years of service as a head of the academic leaders of CEU is between 11 to 20 years, which 40 percent of the total population.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent (%)
Bachelor's degree holder	0	0
With MA units	0	0
MA degree holder	8	32
MA degree holder with PhD units	9	36
PhD degree holder	8	32
With post-doctoral units	0	0
Post-doctoral degree holder	0	0
Total	25	100

Table 4. Participants' Highest Degree of Educational Attainment

Thirty-six percent or 9 of the 25 school leaders are holders of Master’s degree in their field of specialization with some Doctor of Philosophy units. On the other hand, MA degree holders and PhD holders are essentially equal in number, comprising 32 percent. This shows that CEU is compliant with the Commission on Higher Education’s (CHED) guidelines on the minimum qualifications on educational attainment for academic heads or program heads.

Perceived Leadership Behaviors of Academic Managers

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I let teachers know what is expected of them.	5.00	1.87	Agree
I inform teachers about what needs to be done and how it needs to be done.	5.00	1.87	Agree
I ask teachers to follow standard rules and regulations.	5.22	2.35	Strongly Agree
I explain the level of performance that is expected of teachers.	4.78	1.64	Agree
I give vague explanations of what is expected of teachers on the job.	3.22	1.38	Slightly Disagree
I ask teachers to revise and realign the curriculum to suit the needs and demands of online learning amidst the pandemic.	5.11	1.64	Agree
I set deadlines for the recalibration of the syllabi/curricula to be used for the online learning.	4.78	1.76	Agree
I pressure teachers to do well in their online teaching job during the pandemic.	2.89	1.05	Slightly Disagree
I give greater satisfaction for stressful tasks I provide the teachers.	3.44	0.84	Slightly Disagree
I explain the interim or provisional mission and vision of the university amidst the pandemic.	5.11	1.64	Agree
I expect a high degree of certainty regarding procedures, policies and rules on online learning.	4.00	1.64	Slightly Agree
Total	4.41	1.61	Agree

Table 5. Directive Leadership

Table 5 shows that the academic leaders of CEU agree that they implement the directive leadership approach when leading in a crisis, obtaining a total mean of 4.41. Of the 11 statements on directive leadership, asking teachers to follow standard rules and regulations obtained the highest mean, which is 5.22. This is followed by the statements such as academic leaders asking teachers to revise and realign the curriculum to suit the needs and demands of online learning amidst the pandemic and explaining the interim or provisional mission and vision of the university amidst the pandemic, which obtained 5.11 weighted mean.

The results highly speak of the CEU academic leaders’ sense of direction amidst a health crisis. That despite the on-going pandemic, following the standard rules and regulations should still be the norm, although this would mean non-relaxation of some guidelines, which, for some teachers, might be too harsh for a situation like the health emergency.

Directive leadership characterizes a leader who gives followers instructions about their task, including what is expected of them, how it is to be done, and the timeline for when it should be completed. A directive leader sets clear standards of performance and makes the rules and regulations clear to followers (SAGE Publications, 2016).

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I consult with teachers when facing a problem.	5.11	1.64	Agree
I listen receptively to teachers' ideas and suggestions.	5.44	2.35	Strongly Agree
I act without consulting the teachers.	3.33	1.52	Slightly Disagree

I ask for suggestions from teachers concerning how to carry out assignments.	5.56	2.35	Strongly Agree
I ask teachers for suggestions on what assignments should be made.	5.00	1.64	Agree
I email or provide teachers with list of webinars, talks, workshops, training to supplement their knowledge on online teaching during the pandemic.	5.44	2.07	Strongly Agree
I conduct meetings with the teachers before I make decisions on important matters that pertain to their teaching and employment status, monetary benefits, etc.	5.33	1.97	Strongly Agree
I provide support when teachers fail to do their assigned tasks or when they do not perform well in online teaching.	5.33	1.97	Strongly Agree
I review teachers' expertise or specialization before I assign them tasks such as writing online modules, recalibrating the syllabi, and redesigning the curricula.	5.44	2.35	Strongly Agree
I am receptive of criticisms and suggestions from my colleagues.	5.44	2.35	Strongly Agree
Total	5.14	2.02	Agree

Table 6. Participative Leadership

It can be noted in Table 6 that seven out the 10 statements were strongly agreed upon by the CEU academic leaders with a mean ranging from 5.33 – 5.44. The highest mean (5.44) and the lowest mean (3.33) complement each other, i.e. leaders strongly agreeing that they ask for suggestions from teachers concerning how to carry out assignments and slightly disagreeing that they act without consulting the teachers. These actions only prove that CEU academic leaders follows best the participative leadership (5.14 mean) among the three other leadership behaviors.

Participative leadership consists of inviting followers to share in the decision making. A participative leader consults with followers, obtains their ideas and opinions, and integrates their suggestions into the decisions about how group or organization will proceed. Malik (2012) explained that participative leader behavior is also effective as he consults with subordinates in setting, clarifying, and achieving goals.

When an organization is beset by problems, a leader steps up and guides the followers. In this case, pandemic is the obstacle against the realization of the goals of schools, colleges, and universities. Middle managers, particularly the academic managers, have been viewed as critical actors of corporate performance and change (Malik, 2012). Mintzberg (1999) believes that middle managers get direct qualitative information which is priceless for strategic decision-making. Further, they have 'tacit knowledge' which is essential for strategy formation. Thus, their middleness lies in being caught between those below, whose co-operation they need, and those above, who desire from them to implement stated policy/achieve given targets as per deadlines.

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I maintain a friendly working relationship with teachers.	5.78	2.81	Strongly Agree
I do little things to make it pleasant to be a member of the group.	4.33	1.52	Agree
I say things that hurt teachers' personal feelings.	1.11	3.21	Strongly Disagree
I help teachers overcome problems that stop them from carrying out their tasks.	5.44	2.35	Strongly Agree
I behave in a manner that is thoughtful of teachers' personal needs.	5.56	2.35	Strongly Agree
I value the mental health of teachers, especially this pandemic.	5.67	2.74	Strongly Agree
I respect the opinions and beliefs of teachers no matter how uninformed they are.	5.89	3.21	Strongly Agree

I recognize or acknowledge the efforts of teachers in making online learning meaningful to the students.	5.44	2.07	Strongly Agree
I commend outputs of teachers despite limited resources such as Internet connectivity, lack of equipment, and the like.	5.56	2.35	Strongly Agree
I ask teachers how they are every now and then.	5.11	1.76	Agree
Total	4.99	2.44	Agree

Table 7. Supportive Leadership

As can be gleaned from Table 7, seven out of 10 statements were strongly agreed upon by the CEU academic leader-respondents, ranging between an average mean of 5.44-5.89. The highest mean (5.89) was obtained by the statement that CEU academic leaders respect the opinions and beliefs of teachers no matter how uninformed they are. This is a manifestation of respect for diversity, one of the CEU Expected Graduate Attributes (CEU CEEGA). In this connection, almost all of the respondents were CEU alumni in their Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorate degrees.

One statement was strongly disagreed upon, i.e. leaders saying things that hurt teachers' personal feelings, obtaining a mean of 1.11. This holds true because CEU, known as a caring University, is an institution that fosters a quality policy that inculcates strong sense of caring, service, and cooperation.

Supportive leadership consists of being friendly and approachable as a leader and including attending to the well-being and human needs of followers. Leaders using supportive behavior go out of their way to make work pleasant for followers. In addition, supportive leaders treat followers as equals and give them respect for their status (SAGE Publications, 2016).

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I let teachers know that I expect to perform at their highest level.	4.44	1.38	Agree
I set goal for teachers' performance that is quite challenging.	4.56	1.38	Agree
I encourage continual improvement in teachers' performance.	5.89	3.21	Strongly Agree
I show that I have doubts about teachers' ability to meet most objectives.	2.00	2.26	Disagree
I consistently set challenging goals for teachers to attain.	4.78	1.64	Agree
I trust teachers' abilities in online learning.	5.78	2.81	Strongly Agree
I am confident that teachers will do their responsibilities in online teaching with less supervision.	5.67	2.51	Strongly Agree
I set high expectations and high standards for teachers to fulfill.	4.78	1.38	Agree
I encourage teachers obtain an outstanding rating in students' Faculty Evaluation.	5.11	1.64	Agree
I believe in the online teaching competencies of teachers.	5.67	2.51	Strongly Agree
Total	4.87	2.07	Agree

Table 8. Achievement-oriented Leadership

Table 8 shows the diversity of perceptions of the academic leader-respondents. They strongly agree that they encourage continual improvement in teachers' performance (5.89 mean), and they trust teachers' abilities in online learning (5.78 mean). This speaks volume of the respondents' regard for professionalism, continuing professional development, and confidence in their teachers. This result complements their disagreement on the statement that they have doubts about teachers' ability to meet most objectives (2.0 mean).

Achievement-oriented leadership is characterized by a leader who challenges followers to perform work at the highest level possible. This leader establishes a high standard of excellence for followers and seeks continuous improvement. In addition

to expecting a lot from followers, achievement-oriented leaders show a high degree of confidence that followers are capable of establishing and accomplishing challenging goals (SAGE Publications, 2016).

Implications for Enhancing Leadership Practices during a Crisis

The Corona virus outbreak has had a big impact on all business leaders' decision-making skills. In the education sector, the complexity of the outbreak and its unpredictability make it hard for academic leaders to respond. For individuals, like the teachers and students, the experience can induce a sense of loss control and disorientation.

In this regard, middle managers have been viewed as critical actors of corporate performance and change, and this includes the academic leaders in education setting. Mintzberg (1999) believes that middle managers get direct qualitative information which is priceless for strategic decision-making. Further, they have 'tacit knowledge' which is essential for strategy formation. Thus, their middleness lies in being caught between those below, whose cooperation they need, and those above, who desire from them to implement stated policy/achieve given targets as per deadlines. This is evident in the answer of one of the respondents in the survey, saying that he has difficulty of balancing compassion and quality output and of maintaining visibility in the eyes of the top management.

The struggles of the academic leader during a crisis cannot be underestimated. Ensuring that the program outcomes are met despite the limitations brought about by the pandemic, finding alternative learning strategies to be able to meet the program outcomes, top management's disrespect for healthy boundaries i.e. conducting meetings until midnight, looking for qualified teachers to comply with CHED minimum qualifications, struggling with the Internet connectivity, losing time for their family, and coping with stress are some of the challenges that these academic leaders have been facing for the past more than one year of crisis. The extraordinary demands on academic are immensely immeasurable because of the pandemic. This really spells out how good they are as a leader. Responding to a crisis is so much in one's plate.

Leadership cannot take place in a vacuum rather it is a product of situation and experiences. The situation in which job is done and the people, who will do it, cannot be seen separately. The managers who have achieved excellence in one organization may be total failure in other organization because of different situations, like this pandemic. According to situational leadership theory, a leader behavior depends on the situation, so for leaders to be successful everywhere and in every situation, he or she must be flexible to adopt the appropriate behavior as situation demands.

Path-goal theory holds that the leadership behavior of an individual varies from situation to situation. In other words, depending upon situation i.e. nature of problem or circumstances in the organization, an effective leader adjusts his or her leadership behavior accordingly. The path-goal theory relates different types of leadership behavior to differing attitudes and behavioral responses of subordinates. For example, if subordinates lack confidence in their ability to do the job, they may need more consideration and support, but if subordinates' perception about ability is high, a leader should delegate responsibilities to the subordinates, set challenging goals for them to achieve and show confidence in subordinates.

What leaders need during a crisis is not a predefined response plan but behaviors and mindsets that will prevent them from overreacting to yesterday's developments and help them to look ahead (D' Auria & De Smet, 2020). Recognizing that a company faces a crisis is the first thing leaders must do. It is a difficult step, especially during the onset of crises that do not arrive suddenly but grow out of familiar circumstances that mask their nature.

The findings also suggest the need for comprehensive digital media literacy among academic leaders to enhance their ability to lead effectively in a digitally-driven learning environment. Riparip and Caballes' (2024) recommendation for a contextualized and interactive digital media literacy curriculum can be extended to leadership training of school administrators, ensuring that academic leaders are well-equipped to navigate digital platforms and tools effectively. Incorporating digital competencies into leadership practices in the educational institutions can better prepare the academic leaders to manage remote learning environments and maintain high educational standards during crises.

To sum up, the study's findings emphasize the importance of flexibility, adaptability, and digital competence in enhancing leadership practices during crises. Academic leaders must be prepared to adjust their leadership styles and strategies in response to changing circumstances and evolving challenges, leveraging both their interpersonal skills and digital literacy to foster resilience and ensure educational continuity.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The CEU academic leaders are middle-aged leaders who have acquired enormous experiences, in and out of the academe. Their educational attainment speaks volume of their qualification to be academic leaders. In addition, the four leadership behaviors of Path-Goal Theory were all exhibited the CEU academic leaders. However, it is evident that they practice more

the participative leadership, a behavior directed toward encouragement of subordinate influence on decision making and work unit operations, consulting with subordinates and taking their opinions and suggestions into account when making decisions (House, 1974).

Although leaders might exhibit any or all of these four styles with various followers and in different situations, it is not a trait approach that lock leaders into only one kind of leadership. Leaders should adapt their styles to the situation or to the motivational needs of their followers. Different situations call for different types of leadership. Furthermore, there may be instances when it is appropriate for a leader to use more than one style at the same time.

Furthermore, strengthening organizational communication, peer support systems, and professional development opportunities may help employees adapt more effectively to evolving work conditions. Future studies may expand the scope of research by including larger samples, examining additional organizational factors affecting wellness, and exploring the long-term effects of workplace disruptions on employee well-being and productivity.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the colleagues and institutions who provided guidance, feedback, and support throughout the conduct of this research and the preparation of this manuscript. Any remaining errors or omissions are the sole responsibility of the authors.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Arnold Howitt, A., & Leonard, H. B. (Eds.). (2009). *Managing crises: Responses to large-scale emergencies* (1st ed.). CQ Press.
- Day, C., & Sammons, P. (2014). *Successful school leadership*. Education Development Trust, The University of Nottingham. <https://www.educationdevelopmenttrust.com/EducationDevelopmentTrust/files/a3/a359e571-7033-41c7-8fe7-9ba60730082e.pdf>
- Dela Pena-Bandalaria, M. (2009). E-learning in the Philippines: Trends, directions, and challenges. *International Journal on E-Learning*, 8(4), 495–510. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/30504/>
- D'Auria, G., & De Smet, A. (2020). Leadership in a crisis: Responding to the coronavirus outbreak and future challenges. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/organization/our-insights/leadership-in-a-crisis-responding-to-the-coronavirus-outbreak-and-future-challenges>
- Guiab, M. R., & Ganal, N. N. (2014). Demographic profile of public school heads and school related problems. *International Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Research*.
- Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2020). COVID-19 – School leadership in disruptive times. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(4), 243–247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2020.1811479>
- Hill, J., Ottem, R., & DeRoche, J. (2016). Trends in public and private school principal demographics and qualifications: 1987–88 to 2011–12. National Center for Education Statistics, Institute of Education Sciences. <https://nces.ed.gov/pubs2016/2016189.pdf>
- Howlett, D., Vincent, T., Gainsborough, N., Fairclough, J., Taylor, N., Cohen, J., et al. (2009). Integration of a case-based online module into an undergraduate curriculum: What is involved and is it effective? *e-Learning*, 6(4), 372–384.
- Johnson, B. R., Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Turner, L. A. (2007). Toward a definition of mixed methods research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1, 112–133. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689806298224>

- Louis, K. S., Dretzke, B., & Wahlstrom, K. (2010). How does leadership affect student achievement? Results from a national US survey. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 21(3), 315–336.
- Malik, S. (2012). A study of relationship between leader behaviors and subordinate job expectancies: A path-goal approach. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*.
<https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/188064/1/pjcss097.pdf>
- Mandap, A. (2023). Leading the new generation: Understanding the leadership styles of a millennial school head. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 1(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10154522>
- Path-goal theory. (2016). SAGE Publications. https://in.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-assets/67537_book_item_67537.pdf
- Pont, B. (2020). Education leadership in times of uncertainty: Rising to the challenge. <https://www.wise-qatar.org/education-leadership-in-times-of-uncertainty-rising-to-the-challenge/>
- Pont, B., Nusche, D., & Moorman, H. (2008). Improving school leadership. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/40545479.pdf>
- Riparip, E., & Caballes, D. (2024). Level of online media literacy of collegiate students: Basis for a proposed curriculum enhancement program. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(8), 137–150.
<https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0104>
- School leadership in England 2010 to 2016: Characteristics and trends. (2018). https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/725118/Leadership_Analysis_2018.pdf
- Tatlah, I., & Iqbal, M. (2012). Leadership styles and school effectiveness: Empirical evidence from secondary level. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257718282_Leadership_Styles_and_School_Effectiveness_Empirical_Evidence_from_Secondary_Level

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.